

The photoeffect

Harald Schröder

2015

We view the photoeffect:

A metal plate is charged with electrons. Now the metal plate is exposed with light of short wavelength. From the kinetic energy E_{kin} of one electron the initiating work W_A of the electron is subtracted. If h is the Planck constant and f the frequency of the radiation source, then we have the equation for one electron:

$$E_{kin} = h \cdot f - W_A$$

For n electrons:

$$E_{kin} = n \cdot (h \cdot f - W_A)$$

We know the exposed frequency and the power of the radiation source. The initiating work depends from the material. Instead of the initiating work we can use the critical frequency f_g , too. The relation with the initiating work is $W_A = h \cdot f_g$. There are tables of the initiating work and the critical frequency.

Now we want to get the maximum velocity v_{max} of the emitted electrons. First we calculate classical:

$$\frac{mv_{max}^2}{2} = E_{kin} = h \cdot (f - f_g)$$

m shall be the mass of one electron. It follows:

$$v_{max} = \sqrt{\frac{2h \cdot (f - f_g)}{m}}$$

This maximum velocity can be a considerable fraction of the light velocity c . In this case it's better to use the relativistic kinetic energy:

$$E_{kin} = mc^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} - 1 \right)$$

We transform this formula to v , with equation (2) of Schröer [1]:

$$v = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{E_{kin} + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

Now we insert the expression of the kinetic energy in the last equation:

$$v_{max} = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{h \cdot (f - f_g) + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

or:

$$\frac{v_{max}}{c} = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{h \cdot (f - f_g) + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

To the critical frequency f_g or the initiating work W_A we can look at tables. With the relation $W_A = h \cdot f_g$ we can calculate one quantity from the other quantity.

References

- [1] Harald Schröer "Geschwindigkeit und Temperatur" 2009
- [2] Harald Schröer "Particular problems of special relativity theory" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002